

Studies in Pd (II)-7-Iodo-8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-Sulphonic acid (Ferron) Chelate

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The formation of a coloured chelate of Pd (II) with 7-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (ferron) has been studied at pH 3.6-4.5 and a 1:2 (M:L) stoichiometry has been established. The apparent stability constant ($\log K$) of this chelate has been calculated to be 9.0531. An indication of a 1:1 (M:L) chelate has also been obtained in the alkaline region of pH 8.70.

Extensive use of Ferron as a chelatometric reagent¹⁻³ has led the authors to undertake the investigation of the composition and other characteristics of the chelates formed with Pd(II).

EXPERIMENTAL

A Johnson and Matthey sample of Palladium chloride was dissolved in distilled water; the solution was standardised gravimetrically with dimethylglyoxime⁴. Sodium salt of Ferron (B.D.H. indicator) was prepared and its solution diluted to the required concentration.

A Beckman DU model spectrophotometer with silica cells of 1cm. light path and a Philips pH meter 9400 with glass calomel electrodes have been used for the experiments. All the mixtures were kept in a thermostat bath for about four hours to attain the equilibrium. The measurements were carried out at $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$.

The concentration range at and below $10^{-4}M$ has been selected for study as at higher concentrations the reagent behaves as a colloidal electrolyte⁵. The Vosburg and Cooper method⁶ taking 1:1, 1:2, 1:3, 2:3 and 2:1 solutions of metal and ligand, at pH range as detailed above, has been applied and as only one maxima was obtained, it was concluded that only one chelate was formed under such experimental conditions. Further, the following methods have been adopted to ascertain the exact composition of the complex:

(i) Job's method of continuous variation⁷. This method has been applied by taking $1 \times 10^{-4}M$ solutions of metal and the ligand and keeping the total volume at 10 ml.

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Optical density measurements were made at 400, 420 and 440 m μ wave lengths respectively and a graph between the difference in optical density and percentage of the ligand was plotted which gave the maxima at a point indicating a 1 : 2 (M:L) chelate (Fig. 1).

FIG. 1

(ii) Mole ratio method⁸. Here solutions of palladium chloride and sodium salt of Ferron of concentration, $2.0 \times 10^{-4}M$ each were taken. 5 ml. of metal solution was taken in each tube keeping the total volume at 25 ml. and the ligand solution was added with an increase of 1 ml. in each tube and the volume made up by adding distilled water. The optical density was measured for each of the solutions at wavelengths as given above and a graph was plotted between optical density and the volume (in ml.) of the ligand. A break indicating 1 : 2 (M:L) chelate was obtained.

Stability of the chelate with change in pH : The required pH have been adjusted by taking different buffer solutions and mixing as per requirement. In the pH range of 0.65-5.20 sodium acetate, HCl buffer, for pH 6.0 sodium acetate, acetic acid buffer and for pH in alkaline range boric acid, potassium chloride, sodium hydroxide buffer have been used.

The stoichiometry (1 : 2) of the chelate has been confirmed by the above methods. Now with a view to find out the stability of this chelate at different pH ranges the following procedure has been adopted :

Solutions of Palladium chloride and sodium salt of Ferron of $1.0 \times 10^{-4}M$ concentration each in stoichiometric ratio of 1 : 2 were taken at eight different pH. The absorption of the solutions were measured and a graph was plotted between pH and the λ max. of the solution. It was found that the chelate was stable between pH 3-4.5.

Stability constant of the chelate : The stability constant of the chelate was calculated by using Job's method of continuous variation taking non-equimolar solutions. The experimental details remained the same as in the case of the determination of composition. Maxima obtained from these observations (Fig. 2) provide the value of x.

The formation of the complex between the metal ion M and the ligand L may be represented by the following equilibrium equation:

FIG. 2

The general equation for calculation of dissociation constant of the complex is:

$$\frac{Cm^{m+1} p^{n-1} [(pm+n)x-n]^{m+n}}{m^{m-1} n^{n-1}} = K_d [n-(m+n)x] (p-1)^{m+n-1}$$

Now the stability constant of a 1 : 2 (M:L) complex when m=1, and n=2, on simplification comes out to be :

$$K_s = \frac{(p-1)^2 (2-3x)}{C^2 p \{(p+2)x-2\}^3}$$

Where p is given by the ratio of concentration of the ligand to that of the metal. We have taken p=2.

This stability constant is derived by assuming the equilibrium of the reaction as represented by the following equation :

where L is the ligand.

The stability constant (log K) has been found to be 9.0531 for the 1 : 2 (M:L) chelate.

Mole ratio at different pH: Four sets of solution were mixed as per detail in the mole ratio method at different pH covering the acidic and alkaline region. It has been observed that as the pH increases, there is the tendency for the formation of a chelate other than 1 : 2 (M:L). At pH near about 5.75 there is an indication of a 2 : 3 chelate which most probably is due to the presence of both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 chelates at the same time. However, in alkaline region, at about pH 8.70 only one, 1 : 1 chelate is stable. (Fig. 3).

FIG. 3

The composition of the 1 : 1 (M : L) chelate obtained at the pH range of 8.7 has further been confirmed by Job's method of continuous variation, by taking $1 \times 10^{-4}M$ solutions of metal and ligand.

DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 along with results of mole ratio method show that the stoichiometry of the Ferron chelate of Pd (II) is 1 : 2 between pH range 3.6–4.5; another chelate with composition 1 : 1 has been indicated at pH 8.70. The stability constant ($\log K$) of the 1:2 chelate has been found to be 9.0531.

Palladium is a tetracoordinated bivalent ion, and Ferron, like its parent compound 8-quinolinol acts as a very strong chelating agent. During chelation the hydrogen of the hydroxyl group may be replaced by number of metal atoms¹⁰⁻¹² and the coordination

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link may then be obtained between the metal atom and the adjacent nitrogen atom. A five membered chelate ring can thus be obtained in the structure of the complex molecule.

Thus a tentative structure of the 1 : 2 and 1 : 1 Pd (II) Ferron chelate is suggested here :

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